

Modelling disease data with nested structures and delayed reporting using a hierarchical framework

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Abstract

Statistical methods that correct reporting delays are vital in early warning systems for infectious diseases, which enable more effective responses to outbreaks, including reducing loss of life, conserving public health resources and financial savings through changes in policy. Framing correcting delayed reporting as a compositional count time series data problem, we present a general hierarchical modelling framework with a novel structure for systematic variability in the reported proportions. We furthermore extend this framework to allow for nested disease structures and for unknown reporting delays, neither of which have been addressed previously in the literature.

Motivation for this work stems from the operational warning system for severe acute respiratory illness (SARI) in Brazil, where predictions are currently generated independently for the total number of SARI cases and the number of those testing positive for SARS-CoV-2. We present a rolling prediction experiment to demonstrate the potential efficacy of our framework for jointly modelling the two counts together, since reporting information on COVID-positive SARI is less timely and complete than for total SARI. We demonstrate improved prediction performance through including an explicit link between overall SARI incidence and COVID-positive test rates, and through capturing effects of the age distribution of SARI patients.

Keywords: Nowcasting, SARI, COVID-19, Notification Delay, Bayesian Methods

1 Introduction

Disease surveillance systems are crucial in the prevention of and response to infectious epidemic outbreaks. Not only do they ensure relevant authorities and the public are informed about potential public health risks and the severity of outbreaks, decision-makers rely on the timeliness of reporting procedures for an up-to-date picture of all infections. However, delays can occur due to administrative protocols and resource limitations. If not addressed, these delays can lead to misinformation and a disproportionate response by authorities, especially when there is severe heterogeneity in the delays. The challenge of “nowcasting” is to correct for these delays, to achieve an estimate of the eventually-reported cases of infection based on limited available data.

Delayed reporting is treated as a specific modelling challenge in the existing literature. However, from a general statistical perspective, correcting reporting delays can be framed as a compositional time series modelling (of count data) challenge. The data are structured as a total count (per time step) which is conceptually a sum of partial counts, each reported some time after they occurred. Delayed reporting is a common data problem affecting several branches of society, including insurance claims (Lawless, 1994), the reporting of crimes (Wesselbaum, 2023) and the monitoring of migration and asylum data (Singleton, 2016).

Here, our motivation is the issue of disease surveillance, where the total counts refer to the total number of observable occurrences of a health outcome (infections, fatalities, etc.) within a particular time period (e.g., one week). The partial count is then the number of these total cases that were reported with a certain temporal delay. For instance, the total count might be 50, of which 20 were reported during the week they occurred, 10 of which were reported a week later and so on until all 50 are reported. However, we view this as a compositional count data problem and aim to contribute new methodological insights and extensions for general applications with similar data structures.

In general, compositional time series count data is challenging to model due to a) the partial counts being constrained to sum to the total, b) complex correlation structures between the partial counts, and c) having to account for temporal trends and variability in the data appropriately, as we discuss in Section 2. A further complication in the case of delayed reporting is that recent total counts have not yet been observed, prohibiting the use of “of-the-shelf” statistical methods for compositional data.

An example of a disease requiring ongoing surveillance in Brazil is severe acute respiratory illness (SARI). A SARI case is defined as a hospitalised individual with both a fever and cough, where the symptoms have onset within the last 10 days. SARI can be caused by several respiratory viruses, e.g., severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) caused by the corona-virus SARS-CoV, or COVID-19 caused by the corona-virus SARS-CoV-2. In Brazil, reporting of SARI can be delayed, often by several weeks, due to local municipality health authorities awaiting reports of individual SARI cases from hospitals.

Previous work aiming to nowcast SARI cases involve flexible statistical models that account for reporting delays explicitly. Notably, the framework in Bastos et al. (2019) is being used operationally by the Fiocruz institute in Brazil as a surveillance system for SARI (InfoGripe). In addition, a group of independent Brazilian scientists are performing ongoing surveillance for severe COVID-19 and SARI (Observatório COVID-19 BR, 2024), using the modelling framework by McGough et al. (2020). The underlying statistical frameworks used for these surveillance systems are reviewed alongside further existing approaches in Section 2.1.

SARI hospitalizations in Brazil are published as open data by Ministry of Health Brazil (2022). The data involves individual SARI cases, which are typically reported after some delay. Where patients are tested for COVID-19, the test result(s) appear later on, usually after a further delay. Here we aim to jointly model SARI hospitalizations as well as the nested portion of these hospitalizations that are COVID-19 positive. In relation to the

current operational system, our goal is to improve the nowcasting of SARI using more flexible statistical methods, and to simultaneously produce more accurate predictions of severe COVID-19 through pooling of information with the SARI case counts.

This work also aims to address the novel challenge of the length of delays associated with COVID-19 lab results being unknown. Patients records are updated manually with no time-stamp for when the confirmed lab result was recorded. Hence, there is no historical information in the data to inform modelling of trends in the delay distribution. However, we can deduce that the delays in COVID-19 reporting will be greater than the delays for SARI reporting – as they are subject to the same reporting processes but with the additional delay of waiting for the lab test results. We take this attribute into account in the design of our joint model for both types of hospitalization.

The modelling framework presented in this paper represents a substantial extension of an existing state-of-the-art statistical framework for correcting reporting delays, which we review in Section 2.3. We then introduce our full modelling framework and its theoretical benefits in Section 3. The framework aims to allow for multiple and nested disease occurrences (Section 3.1) which are subject to unknown reporting delays (Section 3.2). Furthermore, we expand the choice of model formulation for the delay structure to allow a more intuitive representation over time and delay (Section 3.3). Finally, in Section 3.4 we include age demographic covariate effects to improve nowcasting accuracy for severe COVID-19. In Section 4, we evaluate model performance through a series of rolling out-of-sample prediction experiments for federative-unit level data in Brazil. Finally, we summarise our findings and discuss possible future work in Section 5. A Supplementary Appendix compares a wider range of possible modelling choices for this application and provides full details on implementation of models and the rolling prediction experiment.

2 Background

We begin by introducing some notation to describe the general structure of count data subject to delayed reporting, but for clarity we will use the same arbitrary labels and indices when referencing existing methods for compositional count data from other fields.

First, we call the true number of counts (e.g. disease cases) occurring within time period t and region s the “total counts” and denote these as $y_{t,s}$. These total counts can be broken down into partial counts, $z_{t,d,s}$, reported at different delay intervals d – e.g., d could be the number of weeks since occurrence, with $d = 0$ denoting “no delay”. Therefore, we can sum the partial counts over all possible delays to obtain the total count $y_{t,s} = \sum_{d=0}^{D_{max}} z_{t,d,s}$, where D_{max} is assumed to be the maximum delay. Together, the mean, variance, and covariance of the partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$ can be thought of as properties of the “delay distribution”. In our data from Brazil, $y_{t,s}$ are the SARI hospitalizations occurring in week t and federative unit s , while $x_{t,s}$ are the nested portion of $y_{t,s}$ that test positive for COVID-19.

Stoner et al. (2022) highlight that the delay distribution may be subject to systematic variation over time and space due to changes in reporting efficiency and resources. Moreover, Bastos et al. (2019) note that for Brazil, reporting delays can be greatly impacted by fluctuations in hospital staff absence and workload over the course of an outbreak. Conversely, interventions and awareness associated with the progression of an infectious disease could support local reporting procedures. Similarly, the temporal evolution of the total counts $y_{t,s}$ will consist of both systematic and random variability, both of which need to be accounted for. Systematic variability in the prevalence of the disease could occur over spatial regions due to differing population structures, and movement between regions by infected individuals. Additionally, systematic variability will occur over time due to the natural spread or mutation of the disease, and possible seasonal effects.

Capturing all these sources of variability in the data is vital for optimal nowcasting performance but requires models with appropriate flexibility (Stoner et al., 2022). In

Section 2.1, we review existing methods for correcting delayed reporting that aim to achieve this. We focus on approaches within the Bayesian framework to allow for full predictive distributions for $y_{t,s}$ and/or $x_{t,s}$ given all the available data. This quantification of predictive uncertainty is important in the context of infectious disease surveillance, so that the risks associated with different incidence levels of the disease can be considered and prepared for.

2.1 Existing methods for correcting delayed reporting

Existing approaches to Bayesian modelling of compositional time series count data can be broadly summarised into two main groups: 1) joint models and 2) marginal models.

Höhle and An Der Heiden (2014) proposed two alternative hierarchical approaches to modelling variability in the total counts and delay distribution jointly. In the first they assume a Poisson-Gamma mixture model for the total counts $y_{t,s}$, i.e., $y_{t,s}|\lambda_t \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_{t,s})$, $\lambda_{t,s} \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha_\lambda, \beta_\lambda)$. Then, they assume $c_{t,d,s}|y_{t,s} \sim \text{Binomial}(y_{t,s}, q_{t,d,s})$, where $c_{t,d,s} = \sum_{i=0}^d z_{t,i,s}$ is the cumulative part of $y_{t,s}$ that has been reported up to and including delay d , and where $q_{t,d,s} = \sum_{i=0}^d p_{t,i,s}$ is the expected cumulative proportion of $y_{t,s}$ reported by delay d . Finally, they assume an i.i.d. Generalised-Dirichlet($\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}$) model for $p_{t,d,s}$, the expected proportions reported at each delay. This assumption affords extra flexibility in the delay distribution, compared to a Dirichlet model (which has only one parameter to control the covariance for all of $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$) or assuming $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$ are fixed in time.

However, the approach does not assume/estimate any systematic variability over time in the delay distribution, e.g., an overall trend or relationships with covariates. This was addressed in the second approach by Höhle and An Der Heiden (2014), with a Bayesian hierarchical Poisson model for the partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$:

$$z_{t,d,s} \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_{t,d,s}); \quad \log(\mu_{t,d,s}) = \log(\lambda_{t,s}) + \log(p_{t,d,s}). \quad (1)$$

Instead of an i.i.d. GD model for $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$, here $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$ was characterised by a discrete time “hazard”, governed by the effects of covariates $\mathbf{W}'_{t,d,s}$ that vary in time and delay, i.e.,

$\text{logit}(h_{t,d,s}) = \gamma_{d,s} + \mathbf{W}'_{t,d,s}\boldsymbol{\eta}$, where $p_{t,d,s} = (1 - \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} p_{t,i,s})h_{t,d,s}$. Building on this, Salmon et al. (2015) replaced the Poisson model with a Negative-Binomial to allow for extra variance. However, in this second approach the inclusion of systematic variation in $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$ (through covariate effects) comes at the expense of sacrificing both flexible random variability from the i.i.d. GD, *and* a joint model to separate variability in $y_{t,s}$ and $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$ – potentially reducing predictive skill (Stoner and Economou, 2019).

The “marginal” group of approaches aims to model the marginal distributions of the partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$ directly. This can be interpreted as integrating out the total counts, i.e., modelling $p(z_{t,d,s}) = \sum_{y_{t,s}} p(z_{t,d,s}|y_{t,s})p(y_{t,s})$. Such models should still be designed to capture systematic variability in the total counts, since the predictant of interest is $y_{t,s}$. A well-established example, Bastos et al. (2019), aims to capture spatiotemporal structure in the total counts and the delay mechanism, as well as any seasonal effects, through various flexible functions in the mean for $z_{t,d,s}$. The counts $z_{t,d,s}$ are assumed conditionally independent, given the temporal, spatial and delay structures. The total counts are predicted through $y_{t,s} = \sum_{d=0}^{D_{max}} z_{t,d,s}$. The advantage of a “marginal” model is avoiding a hierarchical structure for $y_{t,s}$ and $z_{t,d,s}|y_{t,s}$, enabling estimation using a wider variety of approaches, such as Integrated Nested Laplace Approximations (INLA) methods. These are usually faster and therefore potentially more suitable for time-sensitive applications, e.g., daily nowcasting, compared to Monte-Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) methods – as used in Höhle and An Der Heiden (2014) and other works.

Stoner and Economou (2019) demonstrated that to capture the variance of $y_{t,s}$ in marginal models correctly, it is necessary to model the covariance structure of $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$ accurately. However, assuming conditional independence in $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$ (e.g., Bastos et al. (2019)) is restrictive in that respect. McGough et al. (2020) attempted to separate the systematic variability of the total disease counts and the delay distribution by decomposing the mean of $z_{t,d}$ into $\beta_d \exp(\alpha_t)$, where β_d represents the mean proportion of $y_{t,s}$ reported at each

delay d . However, this still assumes that $z_{t,d,s}$ are conditionally independent and does not account for interactions between time and delay. This model is therefore unable to explicitly capture systematic temporal variability in the delay distribution, which is assumed to be the same for all weeks within a moving window. A shorter window does allow more sensitivity to changes over time in the delay distribution, but makes parameter estimates more volatile due to the training data set being smaller.

Marginal models do not explicitly model the total counts $y_{t,s}$ so they are theoretically restricted in their capacity to appropriately capture their distribution. At the same time, predicting the total counts through $y_{t,s} = \sum_{d=0}^D z_{t,d,s}$ can lead to excessive predictive uncertainty when nowcasting, and even more so when forecasting, since the uncertainty in the delay distribution is propagated in $y_{t,s}$ (Stoner and Economou, 2019). Here we opt for the joint and hierarchical approach because we believe it is a more rigorous treatment of the various sources of variability in the data.

2.2 Delayed reporting as a compositional time series problem

Compositional data is defined as a set of non-negative parts that sum to a total. Examples of such data include: voting intention polls that measure the percentage of people intending to vote for different political parties (de Vos, 1998); household surveys that capture the percentage of people using different fuels as their main energy source for cooking (Stoner et al., 2020); or forensic data capturing the elemental composition of fragments at crime scenes (Campbell et al., 2009). Models for such data must account for both the sum-to-a-total and the non-negativity constraint. Log-ratio transformations are commonly used to map continuous compositional data onto the real space, allowing the use of standard statistical techniques. An added challenge arises when either there are counts equal to 0 such that the log ratios are undefined, or when counts are small (e.g., rare diseases). In the latter case, transformed data will be strongly bounded and non-smooth so assuming

a continuous probability model (e.g., Normal) would be inappropriate. Here we instead focus on probability models for the original count structure.

Another research area that involves modelling compositional counts is the analysis of the make-up of microbiomes. Here, one common choice is the Dirichlet multinomial (DM) model (Chen and Li (2013), Koslovsky (2023)), which describes the counts directly while also allowing extra variance relative to the multinomial. However, the DM restricts all cross-correlations to be negative (Stoner and Economou, 2019). A more flexible option is the generalised Dirichlet multinomial (GDM), proposed for microbiome modelling in Tang and Chen (2018), as it has a more general correlation structure.

A compelling alternative is the logistic normal multinomial (LNM) proposed in Xia et al. (2013). This assumes a Multinomial($\mathbf{p}_{t,s}, y_{t,s}$) model for $\mathbf{z}_{t,s} \mid \mathbf{p}_{t,s}, y_{t,s}$, where the multinomial probabilities $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$ are linked to a vector $\mathbf{q}_{t,s} \sim \text{Multivariate-Normal}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{t,s}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ through an additive log-ratio (ALR) link function, i.e., $\mathbf{q}_{t,s} = \text{ALR}(\mathbf{p}_{t,s})$. This model is arguably more flexible than the GDM since the covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ can allow for general covariance structures in $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$. However, computing the likelihood of $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$ and inferring the whole covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ in the LNM is challenging (the number of elements in $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ grows with the square of the number of compositions (Zhang and Lin, 2019)). In the GDM, the number of parameters scales linearly with the number of compositions and the likelihood is tractable both in its full joint form or as a series of Beta-Binomial conditional likelihoods, the latter of which is convenient when there are missing values in $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$. To our knowledge, the LNM has only been explored in the context of known total counts $y_{t,s}$, and not within a joint hierarchical model for both $y_{t,s}$ and $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$.

2.3 The Generalized-Dirichlet-Multinomial method

Viewing delayed reporting as a challenge of modelling compositional time series of counts motivates an approach based on the Generalized-Dirichlet-Multinomial (GDM) family of

distributions. Stoner and Economou (2019) used the GDM to model the partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$ conditional on a Negative-Binomial model for total counts $y_{t,s}$, to flexibly capture the different sources of random and systematic variability in the data:

$$y_{t,s} | \lambda_{t,s}, \theta_s \sim \text{Negative-Binomial}(\lambda_{t,s}, \theta_s); \quad \log(\lambda_{t,s}) = f(t, s), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_{t,s} | \boldsymbol{\nu}_{t,s}, y_{t,s}, \phi_s \sim \text{GDM}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_{t,s}, y_{t,s}, \phi_s). \quad (3)$$

The GDM is a conditional Multinomial($\mathbf{p}_{t,s}, y_{t,s}$) distribution, where the mean proportion of $y_{t,s}$ reported at each delay is modeled by $\mathbf{p}_{t,s} \sim \text{Generalized-Dirichlet}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_{t,s}, \phi_s)$. As discussed in Section 2.1, this increases the number of parameters of the model (compared to a Multinomial model) such that the mean, variance and covariance are no longer all determined by just $\mathbf{p}_{t,s}$. Stoner and Economou (2019) argue that this additional flexibility improves predictive performance both theoretically and in practice.

An alternative representation of the GDM is as a series of Beta-Binomial distributions for the partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$, conditional on the already observed partial counts $z_{t,1,s}, \dots, z_{t,d-1,s}$ and the total counts $y_{t,s}$ given by $z_{t,d,s} | \nu_{t,d,s}, \phi_d, N_{t,d,s} \sim \text{Beta-Binomial}(\nu_{t,d,s}, \phi_{s,d}, N_{t,d,s})$. Here, $N_{t,d,s} = y_{t,s} - \sum_{j=1}^{d-1} z_{t,s,j}$ are the remaining counts yet to be reported at delay d . This formulation is used in practice for an intuitive way of introducing covariates and temporal/spatial structures in the delay, and as a more straightforward implementation using MCMC. Here, dispersion parameters $\phi_{s,d} > 0$ inflate the variance of each Beta-Binomial component in turn (compared to Binomial models, which the Beta-Binomial reduces to as $\phi_{s,d} \rightarrow \infty$), allowing for a flexible covariance structure in $\mathbf{z}_{t,s}$.

The resulting expected relative proportions are then defined as $\nu_{t,d,s} = E \left[\frac{z_{t,d,s}}{N_{t,d,s}} \right]$. These are the number of counts expected to be reported at delay d divided by the as of yet unreported counts. The dispersion parameter can in principle also be modeled as a general function of time, space, and delay $\log(\phi_{t,d,s}) = h(t, d, s)$.

Stoner et al. (2022) present an extensive comparison of the predictive performance of the GDM and the models presented in Bastos et al. (2019) and McGough et al. (2020)

through a 15-month rolling prediction experiment on COVID-19 deaths in England. The results demonstrated the separation and modelling of all sources of variability in the GDM model made it capable of accurately capturing all variability in the data and therefore allowing for better predictions with reduced uncertainty.

On this basis, we opt to build on the GDM framework to develop our joint model for related diseases (in this case SARI and COVID-19). However, we also develop an alternative variation of the GDM which aims to bring together strengths and mitigate the weaknesses of the two previously studied variants of the GDM, which differ in the choice of link function for the relative means $\nu_{t,d,s}$ of the Beta-Binomial model, a choice which can have non-trivial impacts on predictive performance and implementation.

2.3.1 Link functions

Specifically, Stoner and Economou (2019) offer two alternative link functions. The “hazard” version:

$$\log\left(\frac{\nu_{t,d,s}}{1 - \nu_{t,d,s}}\right) = i(t, d, s), \quad (4)$$

and the “survivor” version:

$$\nu_{t,d,s} = \frac{S_{t,d,s} - S_{t,d-1,s}}{1 - S_{t,d-1,s}}; \quad \text{probit}(S_{t,d,s}) = i(t, d, s). \quad (5)$$

Here $S_{t,d,s} = E\left[\frac{\sum_{j=1}^d z_{t,j,s}}{y_{t,s}}\right]$ are the expected cumulative proportions defined by the cumulative number of counts reported up to delay d divided by the total number of counts for time t . In Equations (4) - (5), the general function $i(\cdot)$ is open to user choice and represents the systematic time-delay effects on the relative proportions. Possible options include random effects, covariates, Gaussian processes and auto-regressive terms. Stoner et al. (2022) opted for hierarchically-structured penalised cubic splines of time with shrinkage.

The hazard version (Equation (4)) offers a relatively straightforward way to fit flexible models, as it uses a simple logistic transformation to directly model the relative proportions. However, conceptualising intuitive models for the relative proportions is challenging,

especially for later delays when the small number of remaining cases to be reported mean the expected relative proportion could plausibly be very small or very large. At the same time, modelling the relative proportions directly limits options for structures that pool information across delays (e.g., penalised smooth time-delay interactions), to potentially result in a simpler model that is better at predicting out-of-sample. This is because we might reasonably expect the relative proportions to vary in a less smooth or otherwise less predictable way across d , compared to alternative representations of the mean proportions, e.g., the expected proportion for each d , $u_{t,d,s} = E \left[\frac{z_{t,d,s}}{y_{t,s}} \right]$.

Meanwhile, the survivor version (Equation (5)) is more intuitive with respect to conceptualising models for the cumulative proportions (e.g., by exploring the data). However, any terms in $i(\cdot)$ must be constrained to monotonically increase as d increases. Aside from potentially prohibiting some options for such effects (e.g., smooth time-delay interactions), the monotonic constraint may cause inefficiencies for MCMC sampling. The best choice for the link function in the GDM may be application dependent and therefore one should consider the alternative link functions carefully (Stoner et al., 2022).

In the next Section, we present our modelling framework for correcting delayed reporting of two related diseases, as well as a novel choice of link function for the GDM – to compliment the existing “hazard” and “survivor” versions – relevant to both disease surveillance and hierarchical models for general compositional count time series.

3 General Framework

We begin by assuming the same Negative-Binomial and GDM conditional model presented in Section 2.3. As explained in Section 1, our motivation for this framework is to improve nowcasting predictions for SARI hospitalizations (which have a known reporting delay), and the number of SARI hospitalizations that tested positive for COVID-19 (which has an unknown reporting delay), in Brazil. To the best of our knowledge, methods for correcting

such “unmarked” reporting delays have not been previously studied, therefore we believe it is worthwhile addressing this challenge directly.

3.1 Model for nested structures

First, we model the mean SARI hospitalizations ($\lambda_{t,s}$) in each region s independently, using a temporal cubic regression spline with shrinkage $\zeta_{t,s}$, i.e., $\log(\lambda_{t,s}) = f(t, s) = \zeta_{0,s} + \zeta_{t,s}$, where $\zeta_{0,s}$ are regional intercepts. Here, shrinkage means that $\zeta_{t,s}$ is penalised by a single penalty parameter for both smoothness and overall magnitude.

To model the nested disease, we can introduce a new Beta-Binomial layer to our model hierarchy for $x_{t,s} \leq y_{t,d,s}$, which in this case is the number of SARI cases that tested positive for COVID-19. In general, $x_{t,s}$ could represent any systematic subset of a disease or family of diseases $y_{t,d,s}$, e.g., one strain/variant of a disease. This is given by:

$$x_{t,s}|y_{t,s} \sim \text{Beta-Binomial}(\mu_{t,s}, \chi_s, y_{t,s}); \quad \text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s}. \quad (6)$$

Here, the expected mean of $x_{t,s}$ is $\mu_{t,s}y_{t,s}$, where $\mu_{t,s}$ is the expected proportion of SARI counts $y_{t,s}$ that test positive for COVID-19. We choose the Beta-Binomial because it offers more flexibility relative to the Binomial, e.g., to account for unmeasured covariate effects.

This new layer allows us to potentially include covariate effects or trends specific to COVID-19, e.g., vaccination rates or the emergence of new COVID-19 variants. We exploit this in Section 3.4 by including covariates that indicate the age demographic of reported SARI cases. Moreover, modelling the relationship between $x_{t,s}$ and $y_{t,s}$ hierarchically, pools information across the two sets of case counts. This is particularly advantageous in this application as information on the SARI cases is substantially more timely than the COVID-19 test results, as discussed in Section 3.2.

We capture systematic variability in $\mu_{t,s}$ through the addition of the spline for the mean SARI cases times ($\zeta_{t,s}$), scaled by a coefficient δ_s , a further penalised cubic spline of time $\beta_{t,s}$, and intercept terms $\beta_{0,s}$. Modelling $\mu_{t,s}$ in this way allows us to capture any link

between the total number of SARI cases and the proportion testing positive for COVID-19, e.g., in the case where recent peaks in SARI cases are predominantly driven by COVID-19 “waves”. We discuss the effect of including this link on prediction performance for unknown $x_{t,s}$ based on results from our rolling prediction experiment in Section 4.2.

3.2 Delayed reporting of available COVID-19 case counts

The COVID-19 positive counts $x_{t,s}$ are subject to the same reporting delay mechanism as the total SARI counts $y_{t,s}$ (since they are both derived from data for the same individuals), in addition to a secondary delay in obtaining COVID-19 test results. For the SARI cases, a reporting date is recorded in the data. However, there is no time-stamp in the data indicating when the COVID-19 test results for those cases were received. There is only information on the total reported so far, $\tilde{x}_{t,s} \leq x_{t,s}$, which we can interpret as right-censored.

The problem can also be thought of as an under-reporting one, which can be addressed either by explicitly modelling the under-reporting mechanism (Stoner et al., 2019; Arima et al., 2023) or by using a censored likelihood approach (Bailey et al., 2005). The latter does not allow us to model the under-reporting in any structured way, or take into account realistic constraints in the design of this model (Stoner et al., 2019). E.g., for our COVID-positive SARI cases we might plausibly assume that the degree of under-reporting is worse on average for more recent weeks. Here, we opt to model the under-reporting through a further Beta-Binomial model with dispersion parameter ν_s and a reporting rate $0 < \pi_{t,s} < 1$:

$$\tilde{x}_{t,s} | x_{t,s}, y_{t,s} \sim \text{Beta-Binomial}(\pi_{t,s}, \nu_s, x_{t,s}). \quad (7)$$

We assume a-priori, that $\pi_{t,s}$ decreases linearly at the log scale, at a rate parameterised via slope parameter $\omega_s < 0$. Specifically, we assume that the reporting rate decreases from 100%, from the historic time-point we believe under-reporting starts, M , to the present time point, T_{now} . So, $\log(\pi_{t,s}) = \omega_s(t - M)$ for $t > M$ and $\pi_{t,s} = 1$ otherwise. We

obtain predictions of COVID-positive cases by treating not-yet-observed $x_{t,s}$ as unknown quantities in the model, yielding posterior predictive samples given all available data.

3.3 Extending the GDM framework

In Section 2.3, we discussed two link function options for including systematic variability in the relative proportions $\nu_{t,d,s}$, and their respective drawbacks. In this section we introduce an alternative link function for the absolute mean proportion $u_{t,d,s}$ of the total counts reported at each delay – arguably a more intuitive quantity compared to relative proportions. The purpose of this link function in the GDM model is to map $u_{t,d,s}$ from a vector of proportions summing to 1 onto R , enabling the use of general functions to capture systematic trends.

For both the existing “hazard” and “survivor” link function options (Section 2.3), it can be challenging to specify intuitive and general time-delay interactions (or other interactions with delay e.g. space-delay) without running into constraints, including assuming independence across delay (hazard version) or monotonicity (survivor version). Here we propose the centre log ratio (CLR) transformation as a novel link function for the GDM, to directly model the mean proportions $u_{t,d,s}$:

$$\text{CLR}(\mathbf{u}_{t,1:(D+1),s}) = \left[\log \left(\frac{u_{t,1,s}}{g(\mathbf{u}_{t,s})} \right), \dots, \log \left(\frac{u_{t,d,s+1}}{g(\mathbf{u}_{t,s})} \right) \right], \quad (8)$$

where $g(\mathbf{u}_{t,s})$ is the geometric mean of $\mathbf{u}_{t,s}$, D is the number of delays we will model explicitly, and $u_{t,d,s+1}$ – which we call the “remainder” term – is the mean proportion of $y_{t,d,s}$ reported in the remaining delays $D < d \leq D_{max}$.

As with other parts of the framework, we first suggest that $CLR(u_{t,d,s})$ can be modeled by some general function of t , s , and d , in this case $i(\cdot)$:

$$CLR(u_{t,d,s}) = i(t, d, s); \quad u_{t,D+1,s} = - \sum_{j=1}^D u_{t,j,s}. \quad (9)$$

The second part of Equation (9) introduces a sum-to-zero constraint across $d, \dots, D + 1$, which is needed for $i(t, d, s)$, since the inverse CLR function is invariant to an additive constant (this comes from the original sum-to-one constraint for $u_{t,d,s}$).

We can then derive, by substitution, the relative proportions $\nu_{t,d,s}$ – needed for the Beta-Binomials – as $\nu_{t,d,s} = \exp(i(t, d, s)) / \sum_{j=d}^{D+1} \exp(i(t, j, s))$.

Unlike the relative proportions $\nu_{t,d,s}$, we might assume that $u_{t,d,s}$ is similar across adjacent delays, motivating structures such as 2D tensor product smooth functions across time and delay, penalised in both dimensions against over-fitting, potentially resulting in better predictive performance. The CLR could therefore be a compelling new option for the GDM method of correcting delayed-reporting, while also providing greater flexibility in model design for general compositional count data with arbitrary dimensions (or compositional proportions by simply using the Generalized-Dirichlet in place of the GDM).

In the following Sections, we will investigate potential tradeoffs of the GDM-CLR in practical use for correcting delayed reporting, in comparison to established GDM versions.

3.4 Informative population demographics

The flexible hierarchical structure of our model can be adapted to include covariate effects. A notable available covariate for COVID-19 cases is the age distribution of the SARI cases reported so far: 1) Children $_{t,s}$, the proportion of the as-yet reported SARI patients aged between 0 and 18; 2) Adults $_{t,s}$, the proportion aged between 19 and 60 and 3) Elderly $_{t,s}$, the proportion aged over 60. These three variables sum to one for any given t, s (before standardisation to have mean 0 and variance 1), so we exclude the latter. Where SARI cases ($y_{t,s}$) are not yet fully reported, we assume these are indicative of the age distribution of all the SARI cases. This assumption, i.e., that all age groups will be reported at the same rate, may not be sensible, especially if reporting does differ widely across age, which may introduce bias in model predictions.

As noted in a report by the World Health Organization (2020), individuals aged 18 and under have lower risk of contracting and developing severe COVID-19 symptoms; they are therefore less likely to be hospitalised. This, in conjunction with COVID-19 vaccination strategies often targeting the more vulnerable, including the elderly, means differences in COVID-19 hospitalization between age groups are likely to be notable. We aim to capture potential effects of the age distribution on the proportion of SARI cases that test positive for COVID-19 in our model “CLR Age”, using cubic polynomials:

$$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s} + \sum_{j=1}^3 \left[\beta_{1,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Children}_{t,s}^j + \beta_{2,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Adults}_{t,s}^j \right]. \quad (10)$$

4 Severe Acute Respiratory Illness in Brazil

In this section, we compare the predictive performance of a cohort of models in their application to the data from Brazil. First, we aim to compare GDM models based on the CLR link function to models based on the survivor and hazard versions of the GDM method (Section 2.3). In the CLR models, we capture variability in the mean proportions reported at each delay using a 2D tensor product $\gamma_{t,d,s}$, with thin-plate spline marginal bases, i.e., $\text{CLR}(u_{t,d,s}) = \gamma_{0,s} + \gamma_{t,d,s}$. We then compare this to a “CLR No Tensor” model that instead has a independent temporal spline for each delay $\text{CLR}(u_{t,d,s}) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}^{(d)}$. Both these CLR models include an explicit link between the expected mean SARI cases and the proportion of SARI cases that are COVID-19 positive (Equation (6)), but does not include any age covariates. To assess the impact of this link on predictive performance, we fit another model “CLR No Link” that does not include the link term $\delta_s \zeta_{t,s}$ in linear predictor for the COVID-positive proportion. Then, we fit a final CLR model, “CLR Age”, that includes both the explicit SARI-COVID link term and the age covariates. We assume the cubic polynomials for age are the same across all federative units.

We fit two further models “Survivor” and “Survivor Age”, corresponding to “CLR” and “CLR Age”, using the survivor version of the GDM. In these, we model the expected cu-

Model (hrs to run)	Linear predictor for COVID-positive proportions	Linear predictor for SARI delay distribution	Nowcasting MAE (SARI, COVID-19)	
CLR no link (34.26)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s}$	$i(t, d, s) = \gamma_{0,s} + \gamma_{t,d,s}$	225	242
CLR no tensor (25.37)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s}$	$i(t, d, s) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}^{(d)}$	136	51
CLR (33.96)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s}$	$i(t, d, s) = \gamma_{0,s} + \gamma_{t,d,s}$	168	47
CLR age (34.94)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s} +$ $\sum_{j=1}^3 [\beta_{1,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Children}_{t,s}^j + \beta_{2,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Adults}_{t,s}^j]$	$i(t, d, s) = \gamma_{0,s} + \gamma_{t,d,s}$	153	40
Hazard (21.06)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s}$	$i(t, d, s) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}^{(d)}$	85	56
Survivor (4.82)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s}$	$i(t, d, s) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}$	90	49
Survivor age (9.78)	$\text{logit}(\mu_{t,s}) = \beta_{0,s} + \beta_{t,s} + \delta_s \zeta_{t,s} +$ $\sum_{j=1}^3 [\beta_{1,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Children}_{t,s}^j + \beta_{2,j}^{\text{poly}} \text{Adults}_{t,s}^j]$	$i(t, d, s) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}$	84	43

Table 1: Outline of all GDM model versions compared in our rolling prediction experiment. The run time in hours of each model version is given in brackets below the name. Nowcasting mean absolute error (MAE) is for the most recent nowcast date (T_{now}) such that the prediction time difference (PTD) equals zero.

mulative proportion reported at each delay, $S_{t,d,s}$, through $\text{probit}(S_{t,d,s}) = \psi_{d,s} + \eta_{t,s}$. Here, $\psi_{d,s}$ is a monotonically increasing random walk over delay and $\eta_{t,s}$ is a cubic shrinkage spline of time, both independent for each s . The Supplementary Appendix details a ‘‘Hazard’’ model corresponding to ‘‘CLR’’ but using the hazard version of the GDM and a final ‘‘CLR No Tensor’’ model, as well as further results from the rolling prediction experiment. All models considered in our study are outlined in Table 1, including the model structure, the model run time and the Mean absolute errors (MAE). To compare different models, we carried out a rolling prediction experiment using weekly data starting from July 2021. We selected 16 dates between February and July 2022. Our goal is to fit each of the models at each of these dates, only using data that would have been available for modelling at

those time points. Specifically, the available data at each nowcasting date, T_{now} , includes the number of SARI hospitalizations reported up to that date (through observed $z_{t,d,s}$) and simulated under-reported COVID-19 counts $\tilde{x}_{t,s}$. The “true” under-reported COVID-19 counts that would have been available at each date T_{now} is unknown since the historic data lacks time-stamps for reporting delays. To simulate under-reported counts, we multiply the fully reported $x_{t,s}$ by a value that starts at 0.95 and decreases linearly to 0.25 over the 30 weeks leading up to the nowcasting date T_{now} . We then round the result down to the nearest integer. The study of simulated counts limits the realism of our experiment, but on the other hand it allows checks that the simulated under-reporting mechanism is captured by the models adequately (Supplementary Appendix).

We fit all the models to data from each of the 27 federative units in Brazil, such that we have $16 \times 27 = 432$ sets of predictions for both SARI and COVID-positive SARI. This allows us to assess their performance when applied to a wide variety of time series, each with different shapes and scales in the levels of SARI and COVID-positive SARI cases, and each with differing systematic delay mechanisms. We fit models in 60-week moving windows, i.e., rather than fitting models to the whole time series of historic data, we discarded historic data before the 60-week window, up to and including T_{now} . Moving windows are common in recent literature on disease nowcasting, e.g., to improve computational feasibility in complex methods (Stoner et al., 2022), or to keep estimation of time-invariant model parameters relevant to more recent data (McGough et al., 2020). For each model fit, we generated predictions of recent $y_{t,s}$ and $x_{t,s}$ from MCMC sampling. We provide details on model implementation, including prior distributions, specifications for the spline terms and MCMC software for the rolling experiment design in the Supplementary Appendix.

4.1 Age effects and the impact of COVID-19

To uncover insights into the effect of patient age distributions on the COVID-positive proportion in SARI cases, and the role of COVID in driving recent SARI outbreaks, we examine posterior inference for relevant parameters.

Figure 1: Posterior medians for the SARI-COVID link coefficient δ_s , as described in Equation (6), from the “Survivor Age” model.

Figure 1 shows the posterior distributions of the coefficients δ_s , which link variation over time in the total SARI cases to the COVID-positive proportion (Equation (6)). The posterior medians for δ_s are independently positive for the vast majority of federative units – generally in the region of about 0 to 2. These positive values imply that the higher

the total SARI cases, the more of those cases will test positive for COVID-19 on average. However, in the eastern part of the country, there are some negative values – these suggest that viruses other than SARS-CoV-2 are playing a proportionally larger role when overall SARI case levels are higher in these regions. A similar pattern is observed across all nowcast dates, as demonstrated in our Supplementary Appendix where we plot 4 additional dates.

Figure 2: Posterior medians (lines) and 95% credible intervals (shaded areas) for the cubic polynomial effects of age distribution on the COVID-positive proportion of SARI patients from the “Survivor Age” model.

Meanwhile, Figure 2 shows the predicted effect of the percentage of SARI patients aged 0-18 (left), or 19-60 (right), on the percentage of SARI patients that test positive. Here, we can see that the COVID-positive proportion decreases considerably where more of the SARI patients are in the child age group. We can also see decreasing effects for the adult age group. Implicitly, then, the COVID-positive proportion increases as the percentage of SARI patients in the “elderly” age group (60+ years old) increases. In all cases, the 95% posterior credible intervals are very narrow, reflecting the weight of evidence behind these associations.

4.2 Results from the rolling prediction experiment

To evaluate predictive performance, we compared posterior predictive samples for SARI and COVID-positive SARI to the counts that were eventually reported. We base conclusions on three prediction performance metrics: the mean absolute error (MAE), to capture accuracy of point predictions; mean 95% prediction interval width (PIW), to capture the prediction precision; and 95% prediction interval coverage, to assess whether uncertainty is quantified appropriately. Here, by coverage, we mean the proportion of observed values that fall within the 95% prediction interval. We compute these metrics for each model, combining predictions made across the 27 federative units but separating predictions by the “prediction time difference” (PTD) – this is the difference in time between the nowcasting date T_{now} and the recorded date of occurrence of cases. I.e., a PTD of 0 means predicting for the same week that data is available up to (“contemporaneous nowcasts”), and $PTD < 0$ means predicting for past weeks, for which the counts have not yet been fully reported.

The lower row in Figure 3 shows the performance metrics for predicting COVID-positive SARI cases, for 4 of the 7 models, chosen to highlight the comparative performance when including age covariates and between the CLR and survivor versions of the model. For both the CLR and survivor models, the addition of age distribution polynomial effects greatly improves detection of trends in severe COVID-19 hospitalizations, which is reflected in improvements across all three performance metrics.

The upper row of Figure 3 shows corresponding performance metrics for predicting all SARI. Here, we can see that the Survivor models greatly outperform the CLR models. Notably, the mean absolute error of point predictions for contemporaneous nowcasts ($PTD = 0$) is about 50% lower for the Survivor models. Improved prediction performance for all SARI appears to propagate into COVID-positive cases, where the Survivor models also perform better. We present performance metrics for the “CLR No Link”, “CLR No Tensor” and “Hazard” model in the Supplementary Appendix.

Figure 3: Prediction performance metrics from the rolling experiment for all SARI (top) and COVID-positive SARI (bottom) hospitalizations: mean absolute error (left), prediction interval width (center), and 95% prediction interval coverage (right).

A plausible reason for the poorer performance in the CLR models – compared to the survivor and hazard versions – is that here we assumed systematic variation in the reporting delay could be captured by a smooth 2D tensor product over time and, notably, delay. Assuming smoothness over the delay dimension may not be realistic (e.g., in Stoner et al. (2022) there was a spike in reporting of COVID-19 deaths in the second delay), which may be why the survivor models, which assume a non-smooth random effect for each delay, perform better here. To investigate this further, in Supplementary Appendix B we developed a “CLR No Tensor” model that does not assume smoothness across d . In the rolling prediction experiment, this model performed closer to the “Survivor” and “Hazard” models, providing some evidence that the GDM-CLR can at least match the performance of existing methods. Meanwhile, coverage for the 95% prediction intervals was low across all models, for both SARI and COVID-positive SARI. We discuss one possible reason for

this and practical implications in Section 5.

Next, we zoom-in on one region for a closer inspection of how including a link between SARI and COVID-positive cases effects prediction performance. Figure 4 shows predictions of the proportion of SARI cases that test COVID-positive ($x_{t,s}/y_{t,s}$), for the São Paulo federative unit, from the “CLR No Link” and “CLR” models fitted to 4 of the 16 nowcasting dates. It should be noted that, in our framework, accurately predicting the COVID-positive counts $x_{t,s}$ is dependent on capturing both $y_{t,s}$ and $x_{t,s}/y_{t,s}$ appropriately. These two models have an identical GDM structure for the total SARI counts $y_{t,s}$ and their respective partial counts $z_{t,d,s}$, meaning any differences in their performance predicting COVID-positive SARI should only arise from their respective ability to capture $x_{t,s}/y_{t,s}$ well (through $\mu_{t,s}$). The

Figure 4: Posterior median predicted (lines) and 95% prediction intervals (shaded areas) for the proportion of SARI cases that test positive for COVID-19, from the “CLR No Link” and “CLR” models. Dashed lines show the simulated under-reported COVID-positive proportions of SARI.

left panel of Figure 4 shows predictions from “CLR No Link”, we can see that the predictions are basically linear where the $x_{t,s}$ are not yet reported and that including this explicit link, as in the CLR model (right panel), allows the general shape $x_{t,s}/y_{t,s}$ to be captured a lot better.

Using results from the “Survivor Age” model, Figure 5 shows how the SARI and

COVID-positive hospitalization could be nowcasted for São Paulo. In a regular operational setting, we would see the model predictions (solid lines and shaded intervals) and the total reported so far (dashed lines), but not the total eventually reported (points). In this example, the model predictions are very close for SARI but the point estimates under-predict the most recent COVID-positive counts.

Figure 5: Posterior median predicted (lines) and 95% prediction intervals (shaded areas) for the nowcasted SARI and COVID-positive hospitalizations. Dashed colored lines show available hospitalizations reported at time of the nowcast date.

5 Discussion

The emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 virus has introduced a complexity in the incidence and management of severe acute respiratory illness (SARI) cases in Brazil. Supplementing existing surveillance of SARI with nowcasting of the number of cases caused by SARS-CoV-2 – as indicated by positive lab test results – is useful as an indicator of COVID-19 prevalence in the wider population, since more severe cases are more likely to receive a test. However, existing operational early warning systems in Brazil do not model all and COVID-positive SARI together. We argue that modelling them jointly can lead to more

accurate predictions of COVID-positive SARI, drawing on the more timely and complete information available for SARI cases before COVID-19 test results are recorded.

In this article we aimed to develop a general framework for correcting delayed reporting of diseases with a nested structure. To achieve this, we added an extra Beta-Binomial layer in the hierarchy for the nested disease to an established method based on a hierarchy of Negative-Binomial and Generalized-Dirichlet-Multinomial models (Stoner and Economou, 2019). We further modified this new Beta-Binomial layer to account for under-reporting of recent confirmed COVID-positive SARI cases. In doing so, we have proposed the first modelling approach (to the best of our knowledge) that addresses the issue of “unmarked” reporting delays. Such scenarios, where the length of the reporting delay is unknown, constitute a common challenge in real world data collection. For instance, in Höhle and An Der Heiden (2014) only 79.6% of hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) cases had a known date of hospitalization, since recording it was not mandatory. Previously, such unmarked data have been removed prior to analysis where possible (Höhle and An Der Heiden, 2014).

The flexibility/generalizability of the framework allowed us to estimate the effects of overall SARI incidence and polynomial effects of the age distribution of SARI cases on the proportion of SARI cases testing positive for COVID-19. Here, we found that the COVID-positive proportion increases when the overall incidence of SARI increases *and* when the SARI patients tend to include more elderly people. Through a comprehensive rolling prediction experiment, we quantitatively assessed and compared the potential performance of joint predictive models for SARI cases and COVID-positive SARI cases. Here, we demonstrated that including age distribution polynomials and the explicit link between overall SARI incidence and the COVID-positive proportion led to the most convincing performance, e.g., in terms of point estimate accuracy (mean absolute error).

However, we also found that 95% prediction interval coverage was relatively low with an average of 76% for all SARI and 87% for COVID-positive SARI across all models tested.

Prediction interval coverage has generally been appropriate in previous applications of the GDM method to correcting delayed reporting, e.g., Stoner et al. (2022), so the lower coverage for all SARI cases is especially curious. On reflection, we believe that this issue stems from the joint modelling of SARI and COVID-positive SARI. Consider that we aim to predict SARI cases from $p(y|\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}_{obs}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}})$ and that, by Bayes' theorem, $p(y|\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}_{obs}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}) \propto p(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{y}_{obs}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}|y)$. This implies that accurate prediction of SARI is affected by the suitability of the model for $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ given the total SARI counts \mathbf{y} . Since here we have a complete breakdown of the reporting delay for all SARI, i.e., \mathbf{z} , any imperfection in the specification of $p(\tilde{\mathbf{x}} | y)$ will arguably make prediction of y worse compared to a model that ignores the existence of the COVID-positive counts. Future work could look to manipulate the model dependency structure (graph) within MCMC software, such that $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ depends on \mathbf{y} but not vice-versa, to restore coverage back to desired levels. Meanwhile, in practical application of the models presented here, we could achieve a desired prediction interval coverage level by taking more extreme quantiles from the posterior predictive samples for SARI and COVID-positive SARI.

Although our motivation for developing this framework was capturing COVID-positive SARI cases nested within the broader cohort of all SARI cases, we believe it has strong prospects for application to related problems. In the Brazilian context, predictive performance of nowcasts for SARI hospitalizations caused by Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) could also be improved through joint modelling with the total SARI cases. The distribution of ages within these total SARI counts are also likely to be informative here due to RSV occurring more frequently in small children (0-2 year-old's) (Freitas AR, 2016). Alternatively, our application could be extended to incorporate modelling multiple viruses that cause SARI (e.g., adding influenza and/or RSV-positive SARI) simultaneously. More generally, our framework could be applied to considering nested structures arising from different viruses, nested structures arising from different virus strains, or nesting from the

severity of a disease (e.g., mild cases, severe cases, hospitalizations, fatalities).

We also aimed to extend available methodology for flexible modelling of general compositional (count) time series data, based on hierarchical Generalised-Dirichlet-Multinomial methods. Here, we proposed an alternative approach to modelling the mean proportion belonging to each composition, using the centre log ratio as a link function for the GDM. We argued that this may avoid the major drawbacks of the two established “survivor” and “hazard” approaches, i.e., avoiding monotonicity constraints when instead modelling the cumulative proportions over the compositions, and avoiding a lack of intuition when modelling the relative proportions.

We demonstrated this extended framework in the context of a complex hierarchical data problem, with both a stochastic total for the compositions ($y_{t,s}$) and another stochastic variable ($x_{t,s}$) sharing the same parent as the count compositions $z_{t,d,s}$. Furthermore, we investigated the use of a 2D tensor product smooth term – as one possible option within this general approach – to capture systematic variation over the time (t) and delay (d) dimensions relevant to our Brazilian SARI application. Our rationale for using a 2D tensor product was the potential to be flexible enough to capture non-linear changes in the mean delay distribution over time, with the smoothness penalty terms preventing over-fitting.

Ultimately, our models based on the CLR did not outperform established alternatives from Stoner and Economou (2019) in the rolling prediction experiment. Notably, we tested both a “CLR” model with a 2D tensor product of time and delay and an alternative “CLR No Tensor” based on independent splines. For the former, we constructed the tensor product using thin plate spline marginal bases, meaning it is constrained to be smooth in both dimensions. Meanwhile, the latter does not assume any smoothness in systematic time-delay variability across the delay dimension. The “CLR” model with the tensor product performed worse, such that we tentatively conclude that it may be inappropriate to assume smoothness across the delay dimension in this application. We may have seen better

performance had we constructed our tensor product using a less smooth marginal basis for delay (e.g., spherical-covariance Gaussian-process basis functions, available in the `mgcv` package from Wood (2017)).

Finally, to support further extension, adaptation, and application of these contributions, we provide all R code and data associated with the article as Supplementary Material.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Code and data: All R code and data required to implement all models and reproduce the results from the rolling prediction experiment. (.zip archive)

Appendix: Supplementary appendix with details on implementation and further model results, including alternative link functions and capturing the model parameter for censoring of COVID-19. (.pdf document)

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